

Dilemma and Breakthrough: *Problems, Causes and Countermeasures of Faculty Performance Management in Undergraduate Institutions in China*

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Abstract

Since 2009, undergraduate colleges and universities have experienced a development process from imitating and referring to general education to exploring reforms with the characteristics of vocational education and gradually maturing. However, in recent years, the performance pay system has brought a series of practical problems to the performance management of undergraduate institutions: the current performance pay system, in the practice of teachers' performance management, has fallen into the dilemma of not being able to give full play to its incentive leverage; most teachers are not highly satisfied with the operation status of the current performance management system in schools. Teachers lack work motivation and enthusiasm for independent development; stagnation of teaching reform in vocational education, etc. Various things contribute to the dilemma of performance management; therefore, we should make comprehensive use of modern management theories such as humanistic theory, multiple motivation theory and human resources to optimize the objectives, management evaluation criteria, management methods and management organization structure of teachers' performance management in undergraduate colleges and universities, and improve the performance management system system from different levels.

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Introduction

The performance pay system, which has been implemented in China since 2009, is an important "economic lever" to promote faculty performance management and motivate faculty in undergraduate institutions. In the past 10 years since the implementation of the merit pay system, merit pay has gradually fallen into a practical dilemma. In response, national authorities have recognized these problems and have begun to improve them at the top-level design level. The 2019 National Implementation Plan for Vocational Education Reform states that "income earned by undergraduate institutions through school-enterprise cooperation, technical services, social training, and self-run enterprises may be used as a source of merit pay at a certain percentage. On May 18, 2019, the Vocational Skills Enhancement Action Program (2019-2021), issued by the General Office of the State Council, proposed that "when approving the total amount of performance pay for undergraduate institutions, it may be tilted toward units that undertake vocational skills training work." www.gov.cn (2019) Increasing the total amount of performance pay is an external guarantee provided by national and local governments to solve the performance management problems of teachers in undergraduate institutions. However, the root cause of the realistic performance management dilemma lies within undergraduate institutions. To open the "black box" of performance management problems in undergraduate institutions, the researcher investigated the current situation of performance pay implementation, analyzed the characteristics of teachers' performance management problems in undergraduate institutions, and analyzed the deep-seated causes of the problems; proposed measures to reform teachers' performance management in undergraduate institutions by improving the performance pay system, so that it can play the role of motivating teachers again. The study also proposes initiatives to reform the performance management of teachers in undergraduate institutions by improving the performance pay system, so that it can play an active role in motivating teachers.

1. The realistic dilemma of faculty merit management in undergraduate institutions in China

In order to grasp the current situation of teachers' performance management in undergraduate institutions, especially the impact of the performance pay system on teachers' motivation in undergraduate institutions, the researcher sampled principals and teachers' representatives from undergraduate institutions in a city of Zhejiang Province to conduct a survey. A total of 500 questionnaires were distributed for the study and 478 were returned, with a return rate of 95.6% and an effective rate of 92.1%. The results of the survey are as follows.

1.1 Current status of implementation of performance pay system for teachers in undergraduate institutions

1.1.1 Overall satisfaction with the merit pay system is not high

Analysis of the data shows that teachers in undergraduate institutions are not very satisfied with performance pay in general. In Table 1, 5.2% of teachers in vocational schools were "very dissatisfied" with the performance pay system, 10.5% were "relatively dissatisfied", 34.3% were "generally satisfied", 36.8% were "relatively satisfied", and 13.2% were "very satisfied". 34.3%, "relatively satisfied" 36.8%, and "very satisfied" 13.2%. Further interviews and research show that the dissatisfaction of undergraduate teachers with performance pay is mainly due to the gap between their performance income and that of general education teachers. In comparison, local governments and students' parents attach more importance to general education, which causes general education teachers to have more incentive performance income (excluding hidden income) than undergraduate teachers; in terms of total

performance pay, undergraduate teachers are even lower than civil servants in the same region.

Table 1. Satisfaction with the school performance pay system

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Very dissatisfied	25	5.2
Relatively dissatisfied	50	10.5
Generally satisfied	164	34.3
More Satisfied	176	36.8
Very Satisfied	63	13.2
Total	478	100.0

1.1.2 Lack of true equity in pay for merit

According to the data, 3.3% of undergraduate faculty believe that the performance pay system is "very unfair," 6.1% "relatively unfair," 29.7% "generally fair," 44.4% "relatively fair," and 16.5% "very fair." 29.7%, "fair" 44.4%, and "very fair" 16.5%. This shows that in the practice of performance management of teachers in undergraduate institutions, as the awareness of fairness and democratic participation in management is enhanced, teachers are not only concerned about the fairness of results, but also highly concerned about the fairness of the process and the fairness of the starting point for the implementation plan of performance pay which involves their personal interests. However, under the premise that the total amount of performance salary allocated to teachers in undergraduate colleges and universities is certain, teachers' demands for fairness are directly derived into "equal distribution".

1.1.3 Partial recognition of the usefulness of the school merit pay system

The survey analysis revealed that teachers' recognition of the merit pay system in promoting their own work motivation was in the middle. In Table 2, 7.7% of the teachers thought that the merit pay system was "very useless", 20.5% "relatively useless", 42.5% "generally useful", 21.8% "relatively useful", and 7.7% "very useful" in promoting their own motivation. "42.5%, "more useful" 21.8%, and "very useful" 7.5%. This indicates that the function of the merit pay system in promoting the work motivation of teachers in undergraduate institutions has gradually weakened after merit pay has been distributed equally.

Table 2. Validity of school performance pay system

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Very dissatisfied	94	19.7
Relatively dissatisfied	80	16.7
Generally satisfied	157	32.8
More Satisfied	81	16.9
Very Satisfied	66	13.8
Total	478	100.0

1.2 Problems of other performance management systems for teachers in undergraduate institutions

The performance pay system is only one of the pay management systems for teachers in undergraduate institutions to implement performance management. Other teacher performance management systems that can play a significant role in promoting teachers'

motivation in undergraduate institutions include the professional and technical title system, the job promotion system, and the honorary award system. The analysis found that.

1.2.1 The professional and technical title system can highly enhance teachers' work motivation, but the current management mechanism restricts teachers' upward mobility. The analysis found that teachers highly recognize that the professional and technical title system with the function of professional qualification promotion management promotes their own work motivation. According to the data, only 1% and 1.3% of teachers think that the professional and technical title system is "very useless" and "relatively useless" respectively, while 22.0% of teachers think that it is "generally useful" and 22.0% of teachers think that it is "relatively useful". 22.0%, 42.9%, and 32.8% considered it "generally useful", "relatively useful", and "very useful". The interviews showed that except for a very few teachers, most teachers regard the evaluation of higher titles as an important symbol of their career success, which not only highlights the professional status of teachers in schools, but also satisfies their self-fulfillment and high sense of honor. However, constrained by the traditional teacher title evaluation mechanism and the number of middle and senior positions appointed in schools, the professional and technical title system fails to fully stimulate teachers' work initiative, enthusiasm and creativity in undergraduate institutions, and the professional development prospects of some outstanding young teachers are uncertain.

1.2.2 The school job promotion system can promote teachers' motivation to a certain extent, but there are restrictions on the creation of management positions and fierce competition.

The data in Table 3 show that the system of job promotion, which has the function of giving administrative power, is not very useful in promoting teachers' motivation: 19.7% of those who think that the system of job promotion is "very useless", "relatively useless" and "very useful". " accounted for 16.7%, while 32.8% thought it was "generally useful", 16.9% "relatively useful", and "very useful". " accounted for 13.8%. This indicates that, except for some teachers, most teachers in undergraduate colleges and universities are not interested in the job promotion system for administrative positions in the organization and personnel series, and the main reason for this is that administrative positions in schools are set up with a fixed number of posts and categories, which not only have few opportunities for promotion, but also have particularly fierce competition. As a result, many teachers lose their interest in promotion in administrative positions, and thus the actual effect of the system in promoting teachers' work motivation is not very obvious.

Table 3. Validity of post promotion system

Options	frequency	percentage
Very useless	94	19.7
Relatively useless	80	16.7
Generally useful	157	32.8
More useful	81	16.9
very useful	66	13.8
total	478	100.0

1.2.3 The school honor award system can arouse teachers' enthusiasm for work to a certain extent, but the phenomenon of equal distribution is more prominent in practice.

According to the survey data, 7.9% of the honor award system with spiritual motivation function is "very useless", 6.3% think it is "relatively useless", and 36.6% think it is "generally

useful". "More useful" accounted for 26.4%, and "very useful" accounted for 22.8%. The analysis found that teachers generally recognized the role of the honor award system in stimulating their own work enthusiasm. However, in the actual selection process, whether it is professional honors or comprehensive honors, the egalitarian phenomenon is still relatively obvious, and it is difficult to truly evaluate teachers based on their work performance. Therefore, the traditional honor incentive system has limited incentives for teachers.

1.3 Characterization of teacher performance management problems in undergraduate colleges

In the context of a single performance pay system as the main performance management method for teachers in undergraduate colleges, the performance management of teachers in undergraduate colleges has some situations that are contrary to the original intention of the performance management system. The problems are concentrated in the following aspects.

1.3.1 Teacher satisfaction is not high

A comprehensive questionnaire and interview survey shows that the average satisfaction of the teachers in the undergraduate colleges with the performance management system represented by the performance pay system is only 13.2%. This shows that under the traditional performance management system, undergraduate colleges and universities teacher management presents a single-dimensional and lack of systemic characteristics. From the perspective of the professional and technical title system that teachers are most concerned about, it is precisely undergraduate colleges that restrict the application of senior professional and technical titles and appointment positions, which makes it difficult for a large number of outstanding young and middle-aged teachers to obtain professional promotion opportunities. This not only causes teacher dissatisfaction, but also And further aggravated the internal conflicts between school teachers.

1.3.2 Teachers' enthusiasm for work has declined

The survey found that only 16.5% of the teachers of undergraduate colleges fully recognized the fairness of the performance pay system. This shows that, in the face of the performance implementation principle of "efficiency first and fairness", most undergraduate college administrators have chosen the traditional "harmonious performance management" method to create a relatively harmonious campus working environment. This is one of the important backgrounds for the current performance management systems such as the performance pay system and the honor award system to gradually move towards "new egalitarianism". Several aspects of professional behavior such as organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, and organizational loyalty.

1.3.3 The enthusiasm for professional development of some outstanding teachers has faded

The survey found that outstanding teachers have a high degree of self-consciousness in their growth, and their environment and treatment generally do not affect their enthusiasm for work and their enthusiasm for professional independent development. Even the work eager to help young school teachers grow up is voluntary and voluntary. However, due to the actual performance management system of performance pay and the average and harmonious school performance management culture, it is difficult for the extra labor of many outstanding teachers in undergraduate colleges to be reflected in a timely and effective manner. If things go on like this, their own professional growth rate and their enthusiasm for helping others' professional growth will gradually fade under the comprehensive constraints of internal and external factors.

1.3.4 Curriculum and teaching reform in undergraduate colleges has stagnated

The principal is the soul of a school and plays a vital role in the overall development of the school. However, the current performance management system restricts the initiative and creativity of the principals of most undergraduate colleges. Some principals actively promote the reform of vocational education courses and teaching, but limited to the limited amount of performance wages, their bold reform measures are "excessive but insufficient"-the work that they want to promote has no "hands", and they treat those who are not actively working. Teachers can't come up with special incentive measures. Various factors have led to a serious lack of enthusiasm and innovation for managers of undergraduate colleges and universities, and the pace of promoting vocational education curriculum and teaching reform has gradually stagnated.

2. The causes of performance management problems for teachers in undergraduate colleges

The performance pay system is a historical product of the evolution of our country's teacher management system. Restricted by the traditional teacher management system and the old egalitarian and harmonious teacher management concept (Wu et al., 2008), Undergraduate colleges and universities have not specifically issued relevant implementation plans for the performance pay system, which makes the performance pay system for teachers in undergraduate colleges and universities, which lacks policy basis, more difficult to stimulate the enthusiasm of teachers and promote the independent development of teachers. The specific causes of this problem are mainly as follows:

2.1 Performance management system design of undergraduate institutions

2.1.1 Failed to coordinate the relationship between the dual objectives of fairness and efficiency in performance management. The original intention of implementing performance management is to strengthen teacher management and promote teachers' enthusiasm for work. However, in the implementation process, performance pay and other systems are mostly based on promoting fairness and taking performance into consideration. Actually, absolutely fair does not exist, only through a relatively perfect performance management system, the unfair factors in the "cradle", truly fair starting point and fair procedure and results, to protect the lawful rights and interests of the undergraduate course colleges and universities teachers, really build dynamic mechanism for the sustainable development of undergraduate course colleges and universities.

2.1.2 Failed to properly handle the relationship between short-term explicit indicators and long-term implicit indicators in performance appraisal standards

Compared with enterprises or other institutions, it is difficult to measure the quality of undergraduate education with objective data, and school education itself is a subtle and relatively long-term process. In recent years, as the fundamental task of education at all levels and of all kinds, the education object of undergraduate colleges and universities needs to give play to teachers' great love of education without difference. On the other hand, performance pay and other systems only emphasize the explicit and quantifiable performance assessment indicators, but ignore the "silent" moral education of students, which is bound to cause serious absence of undergraduate student management and education work.

2.2 The implementation of performance management for undergraduate teachers

2.2.1 Restricted by traditional school management concepts

Any educational policy will be influenced by the traditional economic, political and cultural environment in the implementation of the region. Because traditional school management pursues one-way and unmanned management, administrative and bureaucratization are its main characteristics. This management mode lacks deep recognition and understanding of the objects of management, especially for the complex and diverse needs of the intellectuals, such as the behavioral motivation and professional attitude of the undergraduate teachers. In the implementation of the performance management system such as salary, honorary award process, managers of old management concept, a lot of college teachers in order to avoid the contradiction between the income distribution, deliberately to create a harmonious situation of school, strictly abide by the so-called "fair" and the default no personality differences "equalitarianism" distribution way, To a large extent, the incentive effect of performance management system such as performance pay and honor award is limited.

2.2.2 Existing performance appraisal standards "narrow" the work of teachers

In the face of undergraduate student groups, teachers' educational and teaching labor is rich. If all the requirements are consistent with the performance appraisal standards, it is easy to lead to undergraduate teachers to ignore the implicit education labor beyond the appraisal standards. Moreover, it is obviously a short-sighted and unscientific management behavior to simplify the sacred mission of teaching and educating people into meaningless evaluation indexes and judge the role of teachers' future education according to the visible results of their current work. In addition, those assessment indicators that are difficult to identify are easy to lead to formalization of performance appraisal.

2.3 Teachers of undergraduate institutions

2.3.1 The needs and motivations of undergraduate teachers are diverse

According to the "marginal theory" in economics, the logical starting point of the merit pay system -- the economic needs of individuals are particularly urgent for teachers in a certain stage of life. Once they go beyond that most difficult stage, their pursuit of satisfaction is not only economic factors (Cheng, 2016). In the whole social system, the self-value realization and development demand pursued by human beings are rich and diversified. The dynamic mechanism factors leading to teacher performance behavior are diversified. In addition to economic needs, there are also many factors such as belonging, emotion, psychology, environment and culture. Teachers in undergraduate institutions are not only "economic men", but more often "complex men" and "self-actualized men" (Edgar, 2009). Besides, different teachers have different needs, and the categories and levels of needs of each person will change with their development conditions (Francis, 2007). In particular, the independent development needs of teachers to pursue "self-realization" is the most powerful dynamic mechanism to stimulate the enthusiasm of undergraduate teachers and promote their independent development, and the performance pay system with a single function dimension obviously cannot meet their diversified needs.

2.3.2 There are various forms of performance behaviors of teachers in undergraduate institutions

The work of teachers in undergraduate colleges is different from that of teachers in general education in both its form and content. In addition to normal education, teaching and scientific research, I also participate in school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, social training and scientific and technological services. The existing management system such as performance pay is difficult to measure the complex characteristics of the educational labor of

undergraduate teachers comprehensively and accurately only through superficial quantitative data. If the performance appraisal standard similar to that of other ordinary primary and secondary schools is adopted, it will not only fail to reflect the particularity of their vocational education labor, but also cause them to turn their work into a "routine" strictly following the performance appraisal standard.

3. Countermeasures and suggestions on the reform of performance management system of undergraduate teachers

The root of the current performance management problems in undergraduate institutions lies in the neglect of the complexity of teachers and the need for self-realization, which ultimately leads to a single reward and punishment tool performance management system in the implementation of performance management dilemma. Therefore, the reform of the performance management of undergraduate teachers must be based on the actual needs of the management object, with the purpose of improving the enthusiasm of teachers and promoting their independent development, and gradually improve the performance management system of undergraduate institutions with the performance salary system as the main body, to achieve a breakthrough in the reform of performance management of undergraduate institutions.

3.1 Basic principles of teacher performance Management reform in undergraduate institutions

3.1.1 Principle of development

According to the hierarchy of needs theory and the hypothesis of self-actualization, developmental needs are the highest level of human needs. The highest purpose of human work is to achieve self-actualization needs, that is, to make achievements in work and finally realize individual self-value by developing individual professional knowledge and ability (Sun, 2010). In modern organizations, people can coordinate their self-development goals with the development goals of the organization they work for. In the process of making contributions to the development of the organization, the principle of value development of life is the first principle that the reform of performance management of teachers in undergraduate institutions must follow.

3.1.2 the humanistic principle

The research of humanistic management theory shows that the main object of any management activity is human. Therefore, the performance management of teachers in undergraduate colleges must follow the psychological law of teachers as human beings and the development law of teachers' profession, and establish people-oriented Management thinking, in the undergraduate course colleges and universities on the basis of teachers' psychological characteristics and psychological essence, give full play to their subject consciousness, actively participate in school management in the practice of the performance management, create a harmonious organization atmosphere, make teachers in the process of participation in school management get spiritual enrichment and development of self-efficacy, multi-level multi-way meet their developmental needs (Wu, 1996).

3.1.3 Principle of multiple incentives

Human needs are hierarchical, and this hierarchy is dynamic; The need is the basis of the motivation and interest, interact with work motivation between each other, form the behavior motive mode of the complex (Huang, 2003) when undergraduate course colleges and universities teachers have a strong professional development needs, will be of interest to the education teaching, and become the dominant factors of its behavior, seeking to satisfy its needs Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory to build a diversified and multi-level need system,

the most advantage of the type need to govern one's consciousness and behavior Therefore, the undergraduate course colleges and universities teachers' performance management to flexible use of various system as a whole the incentive form, to arouse teachers' enthusiasm and creativity of subjectivity as the objective, to help them maximize realize their life values.

3.2 The practice turn of teacher performance management reform in undergraduate universities

3.2.1 From Reward and Punishment to development: Shifting performance management goals

In terms of performance management objectives, different from scientific management theory, which regards human as an appendage of economic man and machine, rewards and punishments are required to improve the efficiency of performance management. Undergraduate course colleges and universities teachers development performance management is to promote diversified development as the core, on the management concept of teachers as the most has the development value of education resources, and teachers' independent development as the foundation for the development of the undergraduate course colleges and universities, this is the teacher's most stable and most enduring power, is also the best measure of school organization and management efficiency; In the management practice, the developmental performance management of undergraduate colleges and universities emphasizes the continuous strengthening of teacher training, further improving their knowledge and skills and comprehensive quality, so as to enhance their education and teaching ability, and maximize their personal value improvement and contribution to the school organization.

3.2.2 From simple to Diverse: Shifting to performance management

As an important achievement of modern management, performance pay system is a typical reward and punishment performance management mode, but its incentive mode appears to be single, direct and mechanical. Although the performance pay system has achieved good results in other fields of organizational management practice, but when applied to the practice of teacher performance management, the unique needs and professional characteristics of teachers, especially the independent development needs of teachers, are underestimated. Therefore, the reform of developmental performance management in undergraduate institutions should bring teachers' diverse needs into the evaluation system of performance salary system. At the same time, we should pay attention to enriching the performance incentive methods for teachers. Besides material incentive, we should also adopt target incentive, honor incentive, work incentive, example incentive, organizational culture incentive and other ways to meet the inner spiritual needs of teachers such as sense of honor, sense of achievement and competence.

3.2.3 From organization-centered to teacher-centered: A shift in performance management evaluation criteria

In contrast, the performance evaluation standard of traditional reward and punishment performance management lays too much emphasis on the organization as the center, resulting in the very clear utilitarian and purposeful occupational behavior of the assessed objects. They often persist in the pursuit of explicit assessment indicators, while ignoring implicit assessment indicators, especially developmental indicators. The establishment of developmental performance management system for teachers in undergraduate colleges and universities, firstly, the structure of performance evaluation indicators should be adjusted, and the developmental indicators of teachers should be included in the performance evaluation index system, which also fits the psychology of teachers' career development. The second is to adjust

the function of the performance evaluation to different from the traditional sexual performance management rewards and punishments to organizational development as the standard ignore the management object individual career development needs, lead to teachers cannot fully understand the value and significance of his work, developmental performance management focuses on based on teachers' independent development, the teacher as a social person and self-realization.

3.2.4 From hierarchy to collaboration: Shifting organizational structures for Performance management

Firstly, we need to foster equal and harmonious interpersonal relationships. In traditional teacher performance management based on rewards and punishments, the management subject and object have a hierarchical management relationship from top to bottom. This unequal hierarchical relationship is particularly prominent in the link of performance assessment and evaluation: Because the top-down evaluation mode is adopted, the subject of evaluation is generally the organization and manager, while the teachers are mostly passive, which also leads to the interpersonal relationship within the school organization in the traditional performance management mode. Second, change the style of leadership. The traditional school management style is mostly paternalistic and authoritarian, while the developmental teacher performance management advocates a "democratic and participatory" management style, emphasizing that the common goal of managers and teachers is to promote the common and diversified development of organizations and individuals. This also determines the mutual relationship between the management team of the school and the teachers' team, which is equal cooperation and team consultation.

3.3 Reform measures of performance management of undergraduate teachers

3.3.1 Government level: further improve the performance pay system for undergraduate teachers

The key is to establish a high performance management system for vocational education teachers and perfect the performance salary system. First, strengthen the main responsibility of merit pay distribution in undergraduate institutions. Undergraduate institutions should strictly implement national and local policies on performance-related pay distribution, and improve the performance-related pay distribution mechanism closely related to job responsibilities, work performance and actual contribution based on the actual situation of the university. Secondly, implement the autonomy of performance salary distribution of undergraduate institutions. According to the characteristic development needs of undergraduate institutions, such as school-enterprise cooperation, technical services, social training and self-run enterprises, the total amount of performance salary should be cut into its secondary units for independent distribution. Finally, according to the development needs of undergraduate universities, the total regulation mechanism of performance salary should be established, and the distribution incentive mechanism of performance salary should be gradually improved to promote development and knowledge value oriented by optimizing the structure of performance salary.

3.3.2 School level: establish and improve the systematic performance management system for undergraduate teachers

The school should establish a series of teacher performance management system including performance salary system, professional and technical title system, professional post promotion system and honor and reward system. One is to further improve school performance appraisal standards. The design of performance appraisal indexes tries to pay more attention to teacher professional development, team cooperation and hidden workload

as well as the construction of characteristic projects of the school. Second, we must implement performance appraisal in a fair, just and scientific way. Performance appraisal and evaluation are the core and main part of performance management of undergraduate teachers. This not only needs to further improve the performance assessment and evaluation program, but also to choose appropriate performance evaluation methods, and through a reasonable organizational structure to carry out scientific assessment and evaluation. Third, in the process of assessment and evaluation, we should grasp the focus of motivating teachers, diversify the incentive methods and internalize the incentive content, pay equal attention to the process and results in the incentive focus, and always make clear the relationship between performance goals and performance rewards. Fourth, establish and improve the democratic participation mechanism to promote teachers' independent development. Organize teachers to actively participate in performance assessment and evaluation, and take performance assessment and evaluation discipline seriously. School leaders and key teachers should set good examples and actively participate in the evaluation work with a correct attitude, so as to give full play to the positive incentive effect of performance assessment and evaluation.

3.3.3 Teachers: improve the ability of self-development performance management

The most fundamental factor to improve the performance management of teachers in undergraduate institutions lies in teachers themselves, because it must be teachers' self-consciousness and ability reserve that ultimately determines their own work performance and professional development level. It mainly includes: first, the independent consciousness of career development. This requires teachers to quickly identify the development orientation in the school, and strive to keep their own development goals consistent with the school development goals; Truly understand their own needs, choose the most suitable career development path; Once the development goal is determined, it is necessary to consciously improve their knowledge and skills, compared with the conditions, and strive for early success. The second is to comprehensively improve the ability of autonomous performance management, such as education and teaching ability, time management ability, self-motivation ability and interpersonal relationship processing ability. The third is to explore the strategies of autonomous performance management in various aspects, such as school goal leading development strategy, high-level needs to stimulate development strategy and democratic participation strategy.

3.3.4 Social level: to further establish and improve the performance of vocational education

In order to fundamentally change the passive status quo of the current performance management of undergraduate teachers, the key to the success of the reform is to establish and perfect the social security system and support system. First, to establish and improve the organizational guarantee for performance management reform. The establishment and improvement of organizational security should not only reflect the development goal of the university, but also accord with the scale, organizational structure and centralization of administrative power of the university. The second is to establish and perfect the cultural guarantee of performance management in undergraduate institutions. The culture of undergraduate institutions generally affects the performance of teachers by influencing their attitudes, behaviors and emotions. It is necessary to create a developmental brand culture, create a good developmental cultural atmosphere, optimize the school work environment, and enhance the sense of belonging and cohesion of the staff. The third is to establish and improve the economic guarantee of performance management reform, especially to ensure that the special fund allocation of performance salary for undergraduate institutions is timely in place. In the performance management system of undergraduate universities, the performance salary

system is still the most critical performance support system, which plays a crucial role in guaranteeing the performance management system of the entire undergraduate universities.

Conclusion

The work of teachers in undergraduate colleges is different from that of teachers in general education in both its form and content. In addition to normal education, teaching and scientific research, in school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, social training and scientific and technological services are also key in determining teachers' performance. The existing management system such as performance pay is difficult to measure the complex characteristics of the educational labor of undergraduate teachers comprehensively and accurately only through superficial quantitative data. This study also proposes initiatives to reform the performance management of teachers in undergraduate institutions by improving the performance pay system, so that it can play an active role in motivating teachers.

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